

3. The specific conductivity and hydrogen ion concentration of the sol diminish both on dilution and dialysis thus accounting for the rapidity of coagulation as a consequence of the decrease of the peptising ions.

4. The autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process as demonstrated by the "S" shape of the viscosity-time curves disappears as the sol is progressively dialysed in confirmation of the observations made in a previous communication by the authors.

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A Modified Photographic Method for Substances of Small Rotatory Dispersion.

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The method usually adopted for measuring optical rotatory dispersion in the ultraviolet is to pass light from a polychromatic source through a spectro-polarimeter and take photographs for various settings of the analyser (Lowry, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1908, **A**, 81, 472). The wave-length at which extinction takes place is measured when the polarimeter consists simply of two nicols as polariser and analyser or, and this is the more usual case, in the case of a two-field instrument, the wave-length having equal intensity in the two halves of the spectrum is determined. In practice it is found that instead of a single wave-length being extinguished at a time, a dark band is obtained the width of which is determined by numerous factors such as the rotatory dispersion of the material under investigation, the magnitude of its rotation, the dispersion of the spectrograph used and the intensity distribution of the light source. The wave-length of the middle point of the band is taken as the required wave-length corresponding to the analyser setting but this is obviously unsatisfactory because of the usual shape of the rotatory dispersion curves. The error involved, however, will be negligible if the band is quite

narrow and well defined which will be the case for substances of large rotation and normal dispersive power. In the case of substances for which the variation of optical activity with wave-length is small, a wide band will be obtained although one might have an appreciable thickness of the substance and the readings will, therefore, tend to become inaccurate. The usual photographic method, therefore, fails for substances of small optical rotatory dispersion. The same arguments apply also to the common case where a two-field polarimeter is used, the only difference being that instead of a broad band, there is observed a large region of the spectrum having the two halves of nearly equal intensity.

FIG. 1.

Thus in Fig. 1, if AB represents the principal plane of the analyser and OC, OD represent the planes of polarisation of the two beams corresponding to the two fields of the polariser, after passing through the substance for a particular wave-length λ , it follows that if OC and OD subtend equal angles on AB, then that wave-length will have equal intensity in the two halves of the spectrum. If, for a neighbouring wave-length λ_2 , the corresponding planes of polarisation are rotated through an angle ' α ' to the positions C'O and D'O, the ratio between the intensities in the two halves will be given by the expression,

$$\frac{\sin^2(\theta/2 + \alpha)}{\sin^2(\theta/2 - \alpha)}$$

where θ is the half-shadow angle. In order to enable an accurate measurement of the wave-length of equal intensity to be made, this expression must be as different from unity as possible for wave-lengths on either side of λ_1 . This means that α must have a high value

which will be the case if (a) the substance has initially a high rotation and (b) it has a high dispersive power. The initial rotation can be increased by increasing the thickness but this is of limited utility since the light transmission is also thereby reduced. However, in the case of a substance having little or no rotatory dispersion the two halves of the spectrum will have nearly equal intensity over a large range of wave-lengths rendering it difficult to spot out the wave-length of equal intensity and increasing the thickness does not help very much in removing the difficulty. This trouble was experienced in the case of β -pinene whose rotatory dispersion curve runs almost parallel to the axis of wave-lengths in the visible and in the near ultraviolet. The usual procedure in such cases will be to isolate light of a particular wave-length by the use of a monochromator or by means of a suitable filter and make a visual observation. But in case the region of small rotatory dispersion lies in the ultraviolet as in the case of sabinene (Padmanabhan and Jatkar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 334) this method is not applicable and either the usual photographic method is followed with a densitometer to determine the wave-length of equal intensity (Lowry and Vermon, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **A**, 119, 706) or a quartz monochromator can be employed in conjunction with a photo-electric cell. In any case additional equipment is needed and hence the following method was devised which does not suffer from this disadvantage.

The method consists in determining the rotatory dispersion of the substance under test having a small variation of optical activity with wave-length, along with a suitable thickness of another optically active material having normal dispersive power and a fairly large rotation to start with the usual photographic method being used. Polarimeter tube end-plates of quartz come in very handy for this purpose. The wave-length of equal intensity now becomes easily measurable. A subtraction of the rotation of the quartz plate due to this wave-length, which can be determined either experimentally or from the data given by Lowry and Coode Adams (*Brhat Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 400), gives the rotation due to the substance alone. The readings thus obtained are more accurate than it is possible with the older method. The proper sign and thickness of the quartz plates to be used in conjunction with the substance have to be determined by a few preliminary experiments. It is advisable not to use a greater thickness of quartz than necessary to obtain a

setting easily measurable on the travelling microscope because, if too great a thickness is used, although the setting becomes sharper, a small error in measurement corresponds to a larger difference in the optical rotation of the substance under test. This method has another advantage also. While taking readings near the limit of transmission, it is often observed, especially on the ultraviolet side of the extinction position, the increase in intensity with diminishing wave-length is so feeble that there is a large gap in the spectrum and the measurement consists in locating the middle point of the gap. By the use of a second optically active substance in conjunction, this gap is considerably reduced since the variation in intensity with wave-length is greater and hence the measurement can be pushed a little further in the ultraviolet.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following table shows the measurements obtained in an actual case with *l*- β -pinene. The experimental details have already been published (Padmanabhan and Jatkar, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I.

Length of polarimeter tube used = 2.5 cm.

α .	λ with quartz plate alone.	λ with β -pinene & quartz plate.	α .	λ with quartz plate alone.	λ with β -pinene & quartz plate.
88.8	5008	4850	148.8	3955	3919
98.3	4765	4650	158.8	...	3811
108.8	4560	4459	168.8	3732	...
118.8	4380	4310	178.8	...	3652
128.8	4240	4143	188.8	3540	...
138.8	...	4028	198.8	...	3510

In the first and fourth columns are given the analyser settings while the second, third, fifth and sixth columns give the corresponding wave-lengths obtained for the quartz plate and for the quartz plate together with the substance under test. From these data the rotatory dispersion curves for the two cases have been drawn and are shown in the Figure 2. C gives the rotatory dispersion curve for β -pinene as calculated from the two curves A and B. It can be seen that the

readings thus obtained lie on a smooth curve with those obtained directly and indicated by crosses on the graph.

FIG. 2.

Rotatory dispersion of β -pinene.

As is shown in detail in a previous communication (Padmabhan and Jatkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 518) the rotatory dispersion of a pure sample of β -pinene can be expressed satisfactorily by the following two term Drude's equation,

$$[\alpha] = \frac{54.7}{\lambda^2 - (0.2200)^2} - \frac{63}{\lambda^2 - (0.1900)^2}$$

where $\lambda_1 = 2200\text{\AA}$ represents the first component in the absorption spectrum of β -pinene. This value has been deduced from spectrophotometric measurements of the general absorption of the substance till $\lambda = 2300\text{\AA}$, on the assumption that a simplified formula of the Ketteler-Helmholtz type

$$\lambda / \sqrt{y} = a (\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$$

(where $y =$ optical density and a is a constant) is applicable to the absorption curve (Bruhat, *loc. cit.*). The identity of the second characteristic frequency $\lambda_2 = 1900\text{\AA}$ with that of α -pinene (Padmanabhan and Jatkar, *loc. cit.*) is rendered likely on account of the great structural similarity between the two substances. From the Drude's equation above the optical rotatory power has been calculated for a number of wave-lengths and compared with those obtained by using the modified photographic method as shown below.

TABLE II.

λ	...	5898	5780	5461	4358	3644
$[\alpha]_{\text{abs}}$...	-19.53	-20.04	-21.38	-22.11	-0.8
$[\alpha]_{\text{calc}}$...	-19.1	-19.7	-21.0	-21.8	+0.6
λ	...	5500	5000	4500	4000	3500
$[\alpha]_{\text{abs}}$...	-20.4	-23.0	-22.5	-17.0	+12.0
$[\alpha]_{\text{calc}}$...	-20.8	-22.7	-22.7	-16.4	+12.5

The agreement should be considered satisfactory in view of the small dispersion of the spectrograph used (100\AA per mm. at $\lambda 4000$).

The error involved in such photographic measurements of optical rotatory dispersion depends in general on the accuracy with which the wave-length of equal intensity can be measured and this varies even for the same substance from region to region of the spectrum. If the extinction at $\lambda 4850$ in Table I is taken as an example, it was observed that the wave-length of equal intensity can be measured correct to 10\AA which corresponds to an error of approximately 0.3 or 1.5% in the measurement of the optical rotation of β -pinene. On the other hand in the photographs obtained with β -pinene alone, there is error of nearly 400\AA in the measurement of the wave-length of equal intensity corresponding to an error of approximately one degree or 5% in the optical rotation. It can thus be seen that in spite of the larger magnitude of the rotation, the use of a second substance

of high dispersive power does help to give a more accurate reading and although it is not claimed that the accuracy obtainable by this method is equal to that of visual observations it seems to be fairly dependable for the measurement in the ultraviolet of substances whose rotatory dispersion is small and for which the usual photographic method does not give accurate results.

SUMMARY.

The usual photographic method for measuring optical rotatory dispersion is not satisfactory for substances whose optical activity does not change very much with wave-length. By determining the rotatory dispersion of such a substance together with another of normal dispersive power and high initial rotation, fairly accurate readings can be obtained. The rotatory dispersion of the latter is then separately determined and by difference the rotatory dispersion of the substance under test can be found out. Readings are given for a particular case β -pinene.

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